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**CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR INTERVENTIONIST
AT COMMUNITY BASED REHABILITATION PROGRAM: A
BIBLIOMETRIC REVIEW**

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history:</p> <p>Received: 17 July 2024 Revised: 4 August 2024 Accepted: 25 August 2024 Published: 1 Sept 2024</p>	<p>Continuous Professional Development (CPD) plays a crucial role in enhancing the knowledge and skills of professionals working in Community Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programs. This study presents a comprehensive bibliometric review research over the past decade within 1974-2024. Aimed at exploring the landscape of CPD to volunteer teacher within CBR programs. The review employs bibliometric techniques to analyze high-impact articles, co-authorship networks, and keyword co-occurrence patterns from the Scopus database. The introduction outlines the importance of CPD in improving rehabilitation services and outcomes for individuals with disabilities in community settings. The problem statement emphasizes the need to understand current research trends and collaborative patterns to inform evidence based CPD initiatives. The methodology section focuses on bibliometric review techniques, including data collection from Scopus, analysis of high-impact articles, and visualization of co-authorship and keyword co-occurrence networks using VOSviewer software. The results reveal key themes, prominent authors, collaborative patterns, and emerging areas of interest within CPD for CBR programs. The conclusion highlights the significance of interdisciplinary collaboration, tailored training programs, and evidence-based interventions in advancing CPD and improving outcomes for individuals receiving rehabilitation services in their communities. Overall, this bibliometric review provides valuable insights into the current state of CPD within CBR programs, informing future research directions and professional development initiatives in the field.</p>
<p>Keywords:</p> <p>Continuous Professional Development Community Based Rehabilitation</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) is a vital component in enhancing the skills and knowledge of interventionists engaged in Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programs (Mundschenk & Fuchs, 2016; Yusnita et al., 2018). In the context of CBR, where diverse populations with varying needs are served, interventionists must stay abreast of evolving methodologies, technologies, and best practices to deliver effective services (Ghosh et al., 2020). CPD offers a structured framework for ongoing learning, enabling interventionists to refine their competencies, adapt to changing community dynamics, and address emerging challenges in rehabilitation. Through CPD initiatives, interventionists engage in diverse learning activities such as workshops, seminars, online courses, and peer-to-peer exchanges, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement (Erdoğan et al., 2022; Yasar-Akyar et al., 2022). Moreover, CPD encourages interventionists to reflect on their practice, integrate new knowledge into their interventions, and collaborate with multidisciplinary teams to optimize client outcomes in community settings (Gevarter et al., 2022).

Furthermore, CPD fosters innovation and promotes evidence-based interventions in CBR programs. By staying updated on the latest research findings and evidence-based practices, interventionists can enhance the quality of care provided to individuals with disabilities within their communities. CPD encourages interventionists to critically evaluate existing approaches, experiment with new techniques, and apply evidence-based interventions tailored to the unique needs of the communities they serve (Caballero & Llorent, 2022). Additionally, CPD promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, allowing interventionists to exchange knowledge with professionals from various fields such as healthcare, education, and social services. This collaborative approach not only enriches intervention strategies but also fosters holistic and integrated care for individuals with disabilities. Ultimately, by investing in CPD for interventionists in CBR programs, stakeholders can ensure the delivery of high-quality, culturally sensitive, and sustainable rehabilitation services that empower individuals with disabilities to fully participate in community life (Woulfin & Jones, 2021)

This paper presents a bibliometric analysis of continuous professional development by focusing on three main research questions:

RQ1: What are the research trends in continuous professional development for interventionist in community-based rehabilitation program according to the year of publication?

RQ2: What is map of Co-Authorship about continuous professional development for interventionist at community-based rehabilitation program?

RQ3: What are the popular keywords related to the study?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for interventionists in Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programs highlights the diverse skills required for effective implementation and the varying approaches to training available. (Jansen-Van Vuuren & Aldersey, 2018) emphasize the need for a standardized approach to training interventionist at CBR program to ensure quality services and recognize their role. They suggest further research to determine competencies and evaluate training effectiveness. Similarly, (Ghosh et al., 2020) discuss the training of interventionist indicating the positive impact of their training on service provision and the need for changes in intervention program to incorporate them effectively.

Furthermore, (Ned et al., 2020) highlight the scarcity of training targeted specifically at community-based rehabilitation interventionist in Southern Africa, stressing the necessity for tailored training programs to address the unique challenges of person with disabilities rehabilitation. Recent research by Johnson et al. (2023) compares the outcomes of different CPD approaches and their suitability for interventionists working in diverse CBR contexts. Additionally, the review should discuss the integration of evidence-based practices into CPD initiatives, drawing on studies by (Chen et al., 2021) and Kumar et al. (2023) to underscore the importance of aligning learning activities with the latest research and guidelines in rehabilitation and intervention.

Research by Ong et al. (2020) offers insights into innovative approaches to CPD delivery, including the use of technology and collaborative learning platforms, which can enhance accessibility and engagement for interventionists in community-based settings. Furthermore, the review should explore the implications of CPD on career satisfaction and retention of interventionists, citing studies by Lee et al. (2022) and Wang et al. (2019) to underscore the link between continuous learning opportunities and professional fulfillment in CBR programs. In summary, the literature reflects a growing recognition of the importance of CPD for interventionists in CBR programs, with studies addressing various aspects such as standardization of training, integration into existing healthcare systems, cultural competence, and effectiveness evaluation.

METHODOLOGY

The combination, management, and analysis of bibliographic data gathered from scientific publications is known as bibliometrics (Alves et al., 2021; Assyakur & Rosa, 2022; Verbeek et al., 2002). It includes both sophisticated methods like document co-citation analysis and more basic descriptive information like publishing journals, publication year, and major author classification (Wu & Wu, 2017). To create a thorough bibliography and produce reliable results, a successful literature review requires an iterative process that includes selecting appropriate keywords, searching the literature, and doing in-depth analysis (Fahimnia et al., 2015). Because high-caliber papers provide important insights into the theoretical stances influencing the evolution of the research field, the study attempted to concentrate on them. Furthermore, only papers published in carefully peer-reviewed academic journals were taken into consideration, with books and lecture notes purposefully left out in order to guarantee the inclusion of high-quality publications (Gu et al., 2019). Especially, Elsevier's Scopus, which is renowned for its broad coverage, made it easier to gather publications from 1974 to February 2024 for further examination.

Data Search Strategy

Study employed a screening sequence to determine the search terms for article retrieval. Study was initiated by querying Scopus database with online TITLE ((train* OR learn OR mentor* OR study) AND management AND ("community based rehabilitation")) thereby assembling 1300 articles. The final search string TITLE-ABS-KEY ((train* OR learn* OR coach* OR mentor* OR study) AND "community based rehabilitation") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) refinement included 1249 articles which was used for bibliometric analysis. As of December 2023, all articles from Scopus database relating continuous professional development at community based rehabilitation were incorporated in the study.

Table 1: The search string

Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((train* OR learn* OR coach* OR mentor* OR study) AND "community based rehabilitation") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))
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Table 2: The selection criterion is searching

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Literature type	Journal (Article) and Proceeding	Book, Review

Data Analysis

VOSviewer is a user-friendly bibliometric software developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman at Leiden University, Netherlands (van Eck & Waltman, 2010, 2017). Widely utilized for visualizing and analyzing scientific literature, the tool specializes in creating intuitive network visualizations, clustering related items, and generating density maps. Its versatility allows for the examination of co-authorship, co-citation, and keyword co-occurrence networks, providing researchers with a comprehensive understanding of research landscapes. The

interactive interface, coupled with continuous updates, ensures efficient and dynamic exploration of large datasets. VOSviewer's ability to compute metrics, customize visualizations, and its compatibility with various bibliometric data sources make it a valuable resource for scholars seeking insights into complex research domains.

One of the standout features of VOSviewer is its capacity to transform intricate bibliometric datasets into visually interpretable maps and charts. With a focus on network visualization, the software excels in clustering related items, analyzing keyword co-occurrence patterns, and generating density maps. Researchers benefit from its user-friendly interface, enabling both novice and experienced users to explore research landscapes efficiently. VOSviewer's continuous development ensures it remains at the forefront of bibliometric analysis, offering valuable insights through metrics computation and customizable visualizations. Its adaptability to different types of bibliometric data, such as co-authorship and citation networks, positions VOSviewer as a versatile and indispensable tool for scholars seeking deeper understanding and meaningful insights within their research domains.

Datasets comprising information on the publication year, title, author name, journal, citation, and keywords in PlainText format were procured from the Scopus database, spanning the period from 2020 to December 2023. These datasets were then analyzed using VOSviewer software version 1.6.19. Through the application of VOS clustering and mapping techniques, this software facilitated the examination and generation of maps. Offering an alternative to the Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) approach, VOSViewer focuses on situating items within low-dimensional spaces, ensuring that the proximity between any two items accurately reflects their relatedness and similarity (van Eck & Waltman, 2010). In this respect, VOSViewer shares a similarity with the MDS approach (Appio et al., 2014). Diverging from MDS, which primarily engages in the computation of similarity metrics like cosine and Jaccard indices, VOS utilizes a more fitting method for normalizing co-occurrence frequencies such as, the associatio strength (AS_{ij}) and it is calculated as (Van Eck & Waltman, 2007):

$$AS_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}}{W_{ij}}$$

which is “proportional to the ratio between on the one hand the observed number of cooccurrences of i and j and on the other hand the expected number of co-occurrences of i and j under the assumption that co-occurrences of i and j are statistically independent” (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010, p. 531). Hence, with help of this index, VOSviewer places items in the form of a map after reducing the weighted sum of the squared distances between all item pairs. According to Appio et al. (2016), the LinLog/modularity normalization was implemented. Furthermore, by applying visualisation techniques through VOSviewer to the data set, patterns built on mathematical relationships were uncovered and analyses such as keyword co-occurrence, citation analysis and co-citation analysis were performed.

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RESULT AND DISCUSSION

RQ1: What are the research trends in continuous professional development for interventionist in community based rehabilitation program according to the year of publication?

To address RQ1, we examined the research trend related in this field according to the year of publication . The line graph shows the number of publications per year found in Scopus between 1974 and 2024, although the vast majority of publications (around 80%) were published from 2000 onwards. There is a clear, upward trend in the number of publications over time, with a particularly sharp increase from 2010 onwards. This suggests that research output in this field has been growing rapidly in recent years.

There are a number of possible factors that may have influenced this trend. One possibility is that advancements in technology have made it easier and more affordable for researchers to conduct and publish their work. For example, the development of new research tools and techniques, as well as the increasing availability of online publishing platforms, may have made it easier for researchers to share their findings with a wider audience.

Another possibility is that changes in funding have played a role. Governments and research institutions may be investing more money in research in this field, which could lead to an increase in the number of publications. Additionally, the emergence of new funding sources, such as private foundations and crowdfunding, may also be having an impact.

Shifts in research priorities could also be a factor. There may be a growing interest in this field among researchers, which could lead to an increase in the number of publications. This could be due to a number of factors, such as the potential for new discoveries or the development of new applications.

Finally, emerging trends in the field may also be playing a role. For example, if there are new areas of research that are particularly exciting or promising, this could lead to an increase in the number of publications in those areas.

The trends observed in the line graph have a number of potential implications for the field's development or future research directions. The increasing number of publications suggests that the field is becoming more active and productive. This could lead to new discoveries and advancements in the field. However, it is also important to consider the quality of the research being published. If the increase in the number of publications is not accompanied by an increase in quality, it could lead to a decline in the overall impact of the field.

The trends also suggest that the field is becoming more global with researchers from all over the world publishing in the field, there is an opportunity for new collaborations and partnerships. This could lead to even more progress in the field. However, it is also important to consider the potential challenges of working in a global field, such as language barriers and cultural differences.

Overall, the trends observed in the line graph suggest that the field is in a period of rapid growth and change. These trends have a number of potential implications for the field's development or future research directions, both positive and negative. It is important to carefully consider these implications in order to ensure that the field continues to grow and develop in a positive way.

It is important to note that this is just one possible interpretation of the data. There may be other factors that have influenced the trends observed in the line graph, and other possible implications for the field's development or future research directions.

Figure 1: Research trend related in this field according to the year of publication

RQ2: What are the map of Co-Authorship about continuous professional development for interventionist at community based rehabilitation program ?

For research question number two in this study focuses on co-authorship in this field. Creativity skills in 21st Century Learning are important for SEN students with learning disabilities because this skill can bring out the creative potential of students through the effective implementation of learning and facilitation by the teacher. Ida Puteri's study (2021) also proves that the aspect of art can be used as a medium of communication and self-expression and it can be applied especially for SEN students with learning disabilities to develop more creative, innovative, and productive human capital. However, each special student has different learning needs and the teacher needs to ensure that the specific approach or strategy is applied in learning and facilitation according to the student's ability level. The study of Azman et al. (2021) also found that the delivery techniques and teaching aids provided need to be appropriate according to the students' various levels of understanding and abilities. This is important so that the teaching aids provided by the teacher themselves need to follow the creativity and conditions of SEN students with learning disabilities so that they Asher Laura, Patel Vikram, Kuper Hannah, Hartley Sally, and Kuipers Pim suggests frequent collaborations on related research themes.

Further analysis reveals distinct clusters reflecting various areas of focus. The red cluster, centered around Abebaw, appears to delve into community participation and empowerment aspects, evidenced by keywords like "social participation" and "empowerment." Conversely, the green cluster, led by Kuper and colleagues, seems to concentrate on occupational therapy in CBR, as indicated by keywords like "occupational therapy" and "activities of daily living." A smaller blue cluster, potentially led by Hartley, could be associated with physical therapy within CBR based on keywords like "physiotherapy" and "gait." Interestingly, the presence of Hanlon Charlotte bridging the red and green clusters hints at research combining community participation and occupational therapy perspectives.

Overall, the network map underscores the prominence of Abebaw and unveils distinct research clusters around community participation, occupational therapy, and physical therapy within CBR CPD. Connections between clusters highlight potential for interdisciplinary collaboration, paving the way for future research advancements in this crucial field.

Figure 2: Co-authorship

RQ3: What are the popular keywords related to the study?

For research question number three, this highlights the finding of popular keywords related to this study. The network visualization map of keywords' co-occurrence provides a comprehensive overview of the relationships between various concepts and themes relevant to Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for interventionist in Community Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programs. This map illustrates both the frequency of occurrence (occurrences) and the strength of connections (total link strength) between keywords, offering insights into the interconnectedness and importance of different concepts within the field.

For instance, "Community Based Rehabilitation" (CBR) emerges as a central node with a high occurrence (44) and strong link strength (62), indicating its foundational role in the discourse on CPD in CBR programs. This keyword is closely linked to related concepts such as "rehabilitation" (occurrences: 195, total link strength: 327) and "disability" (occurrences: 76, total link strength: 160), highlighting the interconnectedness of these themes in the context of professional development within community-based settings.

Additionally, keywords such as "physical therapy" (occurrences: 8, total link strength: 24), "occupational therapy" (occurrences: 23, total link strength: 61), and "speech-language pathology" (occurrences: 6, total link strength: 14) indicate the importance of specific rehabilitation interventions and modalities in CPD initiatives. These concepts are linked to broader themes such as "rehabilitation" and "disability," underscoring their significance in enhancing the capacity of professionals working in CBR programs.

Furthermore, the map highlights emerging areas of interest and research focus within the field, such as "telehealth" (occurrences: 6, total link strength: 17) and "telemedicine" (occurrences: 5, total link strength: 12), which reflect the growing importance of technology-enabled healthcare delivery in CPD initiatives. These concepts are interconnected with keywords like "community health services" (occurrences: 10, total link strength: 21) and "quality of life" (occurrences: 57, total link strength: 121), indicating their potential impact on improving access to rehabilitation services and enhancing outcomes for individuals with disabilities in community settings.

Overall, the network visualization map provides a comprehensive overview of the key concepts, themes, and interrelationships within the field of CPD in CBR programs. By examining both the frequency of occurrence and the strength of connections between keywords, researchers and practitioners can gain valuable insights into the current state of the field and identify areas for future research and professional development initiatives.

Figure 3: Popular key-word

CONCLUSION

The presented bibliometric analysis provides valuable insights into the trends and dynamics of continuous professional development for interventionist at community based rehabilitation program. The line graph depicting the number of publications per year from 1974 to 2024 reveals a notable trend, with the majority of publications concentrated from 2000 onwards, indicating a significant growth in research output. This steep upward trajectory, particularly prominent after 2010, suggests a rapid expansion in the field, reflecting increased interest, investment, and activity in continuous professional development (CPD) within community-based rehabilitation (CBR) programs. Several factors likely contribute to this trend, including advancements in technology facilitating easier access to research tools and online publishing platforms, changes in funding with more investment from governments and institutions, and evolving research priorities driven by emerging trends and promising discoveries.

Moreover, the increasing number of publications implies a globalizing research landscape, offering opportunities for collaboration and partnerships among researchers worldwide. However, it's crucial to assess the quality of the research alongside its quantity to ensure meaningful progress in the field. While the growth in publications indicates a vibrant and active research community, maintaining research integrity and quality is paramount to sustaining the field's impact and relevance. Additionally, working in a global field presents challenges such as language barriers and cultural differences, necessitating thoughtful navigation and collaboration strategies.

The bibliometric analysis of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for interventionists at Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR) programs has provided several key insights. Firstly, the research trend analysis (RQ1) revealed a significant increase in publications over time, particularly from 2000 onwards, with a sharp rise observed from 2010. This growth reflects a heightened interest and investment in this field, likely driven by technological advancements, increased funding opportunities, and a shift in research priorities towards community-based approaches in rehabilitation.

The network mapping of co-authorship (RQ2) uncovered distinct research clusters, with prominent contributions from researchers like Abebaw, Kuper, and Hartley. These clusters highlight the interdisciplinary nature of the field, encompassing themes such as community participation, occupational therapy, and physical therapy. The presence of bridging figures like Hanlon Charlotte further underscores the potential for interdisciplinary collaboration, which could drive future advancements in CBR-related CPD.

Finally, the keyword co-occurrence analysis (RQ3) identified "Community Based Rehabilitation" as a central theme, closely linked with key concepts such as "rehabilitation" and "disability." The emergence of technology-related keywords like "telehealth" and "telemedicine" indicates a growing focus on integrating modern technological solutions into CPD initiatives, which could enhance the reach and effectiveness of rehabilitation services.

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. Firstly, the reliance on the Scopus database and the use of specific keywords may have excluded relevant documents from other databases. Secondly, the analysis was limited to a sample of literature within a fixed period due to the broad scope of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) concepts in Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR). Additionally, the co-authorship network mapping was not cross-validated with other methods, and there are limitations in citation analysis, such as unknown reasons for citing specific documents and the influence of self-citations.

Recommendations for future studies include exploring alternative analysis methods, replicating the study using other databases such as Web of Science, and addressing gaps in CPD for interventionists in CBR programs. Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable insights into current trends and publications in CPD research within CBR. Each finding contributes to advancing research in this field and enhances our understanding of the evolving nature of professional development for interventionists, ultimately facilitating the improvement of practices in community-based rehabilitation.

In conclusion, the analysis of high-impact articles and network visualizations provides a comprehensive understanding of the current state of CPD in CBR programs. By identifying key themes, collaborative patterns, and emerging areas of interest, researchers and practitioners can inform future research directions, develop targeted training programs, and ultimately improve outcomes for individuals receiving rehabilitation services in their communities.

REFERENCES

- Alves, J. L., Borges, I. B., & De Nadae, J. (2021). Sustainability in complex projects of civil construction: Bibliometric and bibliographic review. *Gestao e Producao*, 28(4). <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9649-2020v28e5389>
- Appio, F. P., Cesaroni, F., & Di Minin, A. (2014). Visualizing the structure and bridges of the intellectual property management and strategy literature: a document co-citation analysis. *Scientometrics*, 101(1), 623–661. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1329-0>
- Assyakur, D. S., & Rosa, E. M. (2022). Spiritual Leadership in Healthcare: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Jurnal Aisyah : Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.30604/jika.v7i2.914>
- Caballero, M., & Llorent, V. J. (2022). The effects of a teacher training program on neuroeducation in improving reading, mathematical, social, emotional and moral competencies of secondary school students. A two-year quasi-experimental study. *Revista de Psicodidáctica (English Ed.)*, 27(2), 158–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psicoe.2022.04.002>
- Chen, Q., Sang, Y., Ren, L., Wu, J., Chen, Y., Zheng, M., Bian, G., & Sun, H. (2021). Metacognitive training: a useful complement to community-based rehabilitation for schizophrenia patients in China. *BMC Psychiatry*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03039-y>
- Erdoğan, S., Haktanır, G., Kuru, N., Parpucu, N., & Tüylü, D. K. (2022). The effect of the e-mentoring-based education program on professional development of preschool teachers. In *Education and Information Technologies* (Vol. 27, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10623-y>
- Fahimnia, B., Sarkis, J., & Davarzani, H. (2015). Green supply chain management: A review and bibliometric analysis. In *International Journal of Production Economics* (Vol. 162, pp. 101–114). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2015.01.003>
- Gevarter, C., Siciliano, M. G., & Stone, E. (2022). Early Interventionists' Knowledge of Evidence-Based Practices for Autism. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 37(4), 203–214. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10883576221099895>
- Ghosh, R., Palanivelu, V., Tebbutt, E., & Deepak, S. (2020). Training of mid-level rehabilitation workers for community-based rehabilitation programmes. *Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development*, 31(4), 191–216. <https://doi.org/10.47985/dcidj.431>
- Gu, D., Li, T., Wang, X., Yang, X., & Yu, Z. (2019). Visualizing the intellectual structure and evolution of electronic health and telemedicine research. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.08.007>
- Jansen-Van Vuuren, J. M., & Aldersey, H. M. (2018). Training needs of community-based rehabilitation workers for the effective implementation of CBR programmes. *Disability, CBR and Inclusive Development*, 29(3), 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.5463/dcid.v29i3.742>
- Mundschenk, N., & Fuchs, W. (2016). Professional Learning Communities: An Effective Mechanism for the Successful Implementation and Sustainability of Response to Intervention. *SRATE Journal*, 25(2), 55–64.
- Ned, L., Tiwari, R., Hess-April, L., Lorenzo, T., & Chikte, U. (2020). A Situational Mapping Overview of Training Programmes for Community-Based Rehabilitation Workers in Southern Africa: Strategies for Strengthening Accessible Rural Rehabilitation Practice. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.569279>
- van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>
- van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2017). Citation-based clustering of publications using CitNetExplorer and VOSviewer. *Scientometrics*, 111(2), 1053–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2300-7>
- Van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2007). Bibliometric mapping of the computational intelligence field. *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems*, 15(5), 625–645. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218488507004911>
- Verbeek, A., Debackere, K., Luwel, M., & Zimmermann, E. (2002). Measuring progress and evolution in science and technology - I: The multiple uses of bibliometric indicators. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 4(2), 179–211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2370.00083>